

Multiplicative Kernel Method for Estimating Overlapping Coefficient of k Independent Populations

Thesis for Master Degree of Sciences in Statistics

By

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to the one who was a candle illuminating my path, to the one who believed in me and encouraged me, and who always supported me without limits, my great father.

To the symbol of love, giving, and endless support, my beloved mother.

To those who were always by my side, sharing my joy and sadness, and supporting me with everything they had ,my sisters Ahlam, Manar, Malak and my brother Adham.

I dedicate this work.

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Abstract

AL-Soudi, Heba Zuhair. Multiplicative Kernel Method for Estimating Overlapping Coefficient Of k Independent Populations. Master of Science Thesis, Department of Statistics, Yarmouk University, 2025. (Supervisor: Prof. Omar M. Eidous)

In this thesis, we are focused on studying the estimation of the Weitzman overlapping coefficient in the case that there are k independent populations, which is given by $\Delta_k = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx$, where $f_j(x), j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ are continuous probability density functions. The estimation process needs the presence of k corresponding independent samples. To avoid assuming any parametric statistical distribution for $f_j(x)$, we used the nonparametric multiplicative kernel method to perform the estimation process of Δ_k . Since it is difficult to deal with the above integral, we used two different methods to express the amount of that integral as a first step. In the second step, we used the multiplicative kernel method to find a formula for the Δ_k estimator. The method we followed led to several Δ_k estimators. The properties of the resulting estimators were studied, and their quality was compared with the corresponding estimators resulting from the classical kernel method using numerical examples and an extended simulation study. The data was generated from several statistical distributions, with various parameter values, and also with different sample sizes. The simulation results clearly showed the superiority of the estimators proposed using the multiplicative kernel over those generated using the classical kernel for the majority of the cases studied.

Keywords: Weitzman Overlapping Coefficient, Multiplicative Kernel Estimator, Approximation Method, Relative Bias, Relative Mean Square Error, Efficiency

الملخص

السودي , هبه زهير. طريقة النواة المضاعفة لتقدير معامل التداخل لعدد k من المجتمعات المستقلة. رسالة ماجستير في العلوم , قسم الإحصاء , جامعة اليرموك. 2025 (المشرف : الاستاذ الدكتور عمر محمد اعدوس)

في هذه الرسالة ، تركز اهتمامنا على دراسة تقدير معامل التداخل المعروف باسم ويتزمان في حالة وجود k من المجتمعات المستقلة عن بعضها البعض، والذي يعطى بالعلاقة

$$\Delta_k = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx$$

حيث $f_j(x), j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ هو اقتران كثافة احتمالية متصل . تحتاج عملية التقدير إلى وجود عينات مستقلة مقابلة. لتجنب افتراض أي توزيع إحصائي معلمي لـ $f_j(x)$ ، استخدمنا طريقة النواة المضاعفة غير المعلمية لإجراء عملية تقدير للمعلمة Δ_k . ونظرًا لصعوبة التعامل مع Δ_k ، استخدمنا طريقتين مختلفتين للتعبير عن مقدار Δ_k كخطوة أولى. وفي الخطوة الثانية، استخدمنا طريقة النواة المضاعفة لإيجاد صيغة جديدة لمقدر Δ_k وأدت الطريقة التي اتبعناها إلى عدة مقدرات للمعامل Δ_k . تمت دراسة خصائص المقدرات الناتجة ومقارنة جودتها مع المقدرات المقابلة لها الناتجة عن طريقة النواة الكلاسيكية باستخدام الأمثلة العددية ودراسة محاكاة موسعة. تم توليد البيانات من عدة توزيعات إحصائية، مع قيم معلمات مختلفة، وكذلك بأحجام عينات مختلفة. أظهرت نتائج المحاكاة بوضوح تفوق المقدرات المقترحة باستخدام النواة المضاعفة على المقدرات الناتجة باستخدام النواة الكلاسيكية في غالبية الحالات التي تمت دراستها.

الكلمات المفتاحية: معامل التداخل وتزمان، مقدر النواة المضاعفة، طريقة التقريب، التحيز النسبي ، متوسط الأخطاء المربعة النسبية ، كفاءة .

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction And Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

The overlapping coefficient (OVL) is a key statistical measure used to quantify the similarity or shared area between two probability density functions (pdfs). It serves as an indicator of closeness or homogeneity between distributions and has found applications across diverse fields including genetics (Federer et al., 1963), reliability analysis (Ichikawa, 1993), and ecology (Pianka, 1973). In economics, the OVL has been employed to study disparities (Mulekar & Mishra, 1994; Mulekar & Fukasawa, 2010; Inman & Bradley, 1989), while Sneath (1977) applied it to measure disjunction. In addition, Samawi et al. (2011) developed a new nonparametric test of symmetry based on OVL using Kernel density estimation. The overlapping coefficients were also utilized as an important tool in goodness of fit test for two independent populations (Alodat et al., 2022).

Three primary OVL measures have been widely studied: Matusita's measure (ρ) (1955), Morisita's measure (λ) (1959), and Weitzman's measure (Δ) (1970). These

have been extensively analyzed and applied in recent research (Eidous & Alshorman, 2022; Eidous & Daradkeh, 2022; Eidous & Magableh, 2023; Eidous & Ananbeh, 2024b; Eidous & Magableh, 2024). Additional indices, such as the Pianka and Kullback-Leibler overlap measures, have also been investigated (Eidous & Abu Al Hayja'a, 2023a).

Among these, Weitzman's Δ is particularly notable for its simplicity and adaptability to more than two distributions (Inman & Bradley, 1989; Eidous & Alsheyyab, 2025). It represents the area of intersection between two pdfs and is frequently applied in reliability analysis, especially within the stress-strength model to evaluate failure probability (Ichikawa, 1993).

Let $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ be two continuous probability density functions (*pdf*) then the formula of each OVL measure (coefficient) is defined as follows:

- (Matusita's measure, 1955): $\rho = \int \sqrt{f_1(x)f_2(x)} dx .$
- (Morisita's measure, 1959) : $\lambda = \frac{2 \int f_1(x)f_2(x) dx}{\int [f_1(x)]^2 dx + \int [f_2(x)]^2 dx} .$
- (Weitzman's measure, 1970): $\Delta_2 = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x)\} dx .$

The Weitzman's measure Δ_2 is of special interest, (Δ_k is the Weitzman measure between k continuous probability density functions) it is easy to interpret and generalize to more than two probability density functions, is the most widely used coefficient in the literature (Inman & Bradly, 1989; Eidous & Ananbeh, 2024). In this work, we will focus on the Weitzman's overlapping coefficient.

Each of the aforementioned measures has a value between 0 and 1. If the OVL value is 0, it means that there is no overlap between the two densities and that the two populations are completely distinct. On the other hand, if the OVL value is 1, it means that the population densities of the two samples correspond perfectly.

1.2 Illustrative Example And Estimation Of Δ_2

1.2.1 Illustrative example

Let X_1 , be a random variable follows $N(0,1)$ and let X_2 be another random variable with $N(0.5, 2)$, where the two variables are independent. The Weitzman OVL coefficient Δ_2 between X_1 , and X_2 is the intersection region between $N(0,1)$ and $N(0.5, 2)$ as depicted by the shaded area of Figure (1.1). Since the normal parameters are known, we can compute the exact value of Δ_2 as follows,

Figure (1.1). The shaded area represents Δ_2 between $N(0,1)$ and $N(0.5, 2)$.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_2 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x)\} dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{N(0, 1), N(0.5, 2)\} dx.\end{aligned}$$

Let $a = -1.62$ and $b = 1.25$ are the approximate intersection points between $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ as given in Figure (1.1). Each of these two intersection points can be obtained by equating the two probability density functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ and solving the equation with respect to x . These values are obtained by using Mathematica, Version 13. Now, we must divide the interval $x \in (-\infty, \infty)$ into $(-\infty, -1.62)$, $(-1.62, 1.25)$ and $(1.25, \infty)$ at which,

$$\min\{N(0, 1), N(0.5, 2)\} = \begin{cases} N(0, 1) & , \quad -\infty < x < -1.62 \\ N(0.5, 2) & , \quad -1.62 < x < 1.25 . \\ N(0, 1) & , \quad 1.25 < x < \infty \end{cases}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_2 &= \int \min\{N(0, 1), N(0.5, 2)\} dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{-1.62} N(0, 1) dx + \int_{-1.62}^{1.25} N(0.5, 2) dx + \int_{1.25}^{\infty} N(0, 1) dx \\
&= \Phi(-1.62) - \Phi(-\infty) + \Phi\left(\frac{1.25 - 0.5}{\sqrt{2}}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{-1.62 - 0.5}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + \Phi(\infty) - \Phi(1.25) \\
&\cong 0.659664
\end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi(u)$ is the cumulative standard normal distribution at u . For some approximations of $\Phi(u)$. see Momani (2024) and Bani-Salameh (2024).

1.2.2 Methods of estimation for Δ_2

Parametric Method for Estimating Δ_2 : Let $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}, i = 1, 2$ be two independent random samples each from a *pdf* $f_i(x, \theta_i), i = 1, 2$ respectively, where the functional form of $f_i(x, \theta_i)$ is known with unknown parameter θ_i (θ_i may be a vector). The Weitzman coefficient Δ_2 is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_2 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x, \theta_1), f_2(x, \theta_2)\} dx & (1.1) \\
&= \omega(\theta_1, \theta_2)
\end{aligned}$$

Where the new parameter $\omega(\theta_1, \theta_2)$ is a function of θ_1 and θ_2 , which needs to be estimated by using the two samples. For instance, if the maximum likelihood (ML) method is used and if $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are the ML estimators of θ_1 and θ_2

respectively then $\widehat{\Delta}_2 = \omega(\widehat{\theta}_1, \widehat{\theta}_2)$ is the maximum likelihood estimator of $\Delta_2 = \omega(\theta_1, \theta_2)$.

Since we assume that the functional forms of $f_i, i = 1, 2$ are known but only with unknown parameters, this technique is called parametric method.

Nonparametric Method for Estimating Δ_2 : In practice, the functional forms of $f_1(x, \theta_1)$ and $f_2(x, \theta_2)$ are not always known or not easy to determine. In this case, we can use the nonparametric method to estimate Δ_2 , by which each probability density function is estimated based on the corresponding random sample. In other words, this method leaves the data to talk about the shape of their probability density functions.

Let $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}, i = 1, 2$ be two independent random samples each from a *pdf* $f_i(x), i = 1, 2$, respectively, where the functional form of each $f_i(x)$ is unknown. If $\widehat{f}_1(x)$ and $\widehat{f}_2(x)$ are the nonparametric estimators (based on $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}, i = 1, 2$) of the two probability density functions $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ respectively, the nonparametric estimator for Δ_2 can be given as,

$$\widehat{\Delta}_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{\widehat{f}_1(x), \widehat{f}_2(x)\} dx. \quad (1.2)$$

However, in general, it is not easy to obtain the value of the last integral as a function of the two samples $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}, i = 1, 2$. Therefore, some ideas have

been developed in the literature to deal with such an estimator given in formula (1.2).

1.3. Literature Review

1.3.1 Parametric methods

The parametric estimation of the overlapping coefficient Δ_2 has been extensively explored in the literature. These methods assume knowledge of the functional form of the distributions involved and often impose conditions such as equal means, variances, or shape parameters.

Inman and Bradley (1989) were among the first to derive the maximum likelihood estimator of Δ and Δ_2 for two normal distributions with different means and equal variances. Reiser and Faraggi (1999) constructed generalized confidence intervals for Δ and Δ_2 under the assumption of common variance in normal distributions. Similarly, Mulekar and Mishra (1994, 2000) developed resampling techniques, including jackknife, bootstrap, and transformation methods, to estimate confidence intervals for Δ and Δ_2 when the underlying normal distributions have equal means.

Beyond the normal case, Al-Saidy et al. (2005) examined Δ_2 for two Weibull distributions with the same shape parameters. Chaubey et al. (2008) investigated the case of two inverse Gaussian distributions with equal means, while Helu and

Samawi (2011) studied the effect of different sampling strategies on the estimation of Δ and Δ_2 under two Lomax distributions. Dhaker et al. (2019, 2021) focused on the estimation problem for two inverse Lomax distributions. Wang and Tian (2017) introduced a generalized inference framework using bootstrap methods for confidence interval construction for Δ under normality. Montoya et al. (2019) proposed new point estimators and confidence intervals for Δ under various distributional settings.

Recent studies have sought to estimate Δ without imposing parameter restrictions. Al-Magableh (2021) approached the estimation of Δ for two Weibull distributions without assuming knowledge of their parameters, expressing Δ as an expected value and estimating it numerically. Building on this, Eidous and Abu Al-Hayja'a (2023a) used integral approximation methods to estimate Δ under the same distributional framework. Eidous and Al-Daradkeh (2022) extended this technique to two normal distributions, similarly avoiding assumptions on their parameters.

To address the limitations of parameter restrictions, Eidous and Daradkeh (2024) proposed a general method for estimating Δ_2 under normal distributions without requiring equality of means or variances. They reformulated Δ_2 as the expected value of a function and used the method of moments for estimation. This flexible framework was further applied to both normal and Weibull distributions in

subsequent works by Eidous and Abu Al-Hayja'a (2023b), Eidous and Alshorman (2023), Maqableh and Eidous (2024), and Eidous and Daradkeh (2024).

Complementing these frequentist approaches, Inácio and Guillén (2022) introduced a Bayesian nonparametric framework using Dirichlet process mixtures of additive normal models to estimate both Δ . Their approach provides a highly flexible alternative by relaxing the need for strict parametric forms.

In summary, the estimation of Δ has evolved from classical parametric techniques with strong assumptions to more robust and flexible methodologies that accommodate a wide variety of distributional forms and parameter configurations.

1.3.2 Nonparametric methods

When the functional form of probability density functions is unknown or difficult to determine for specific datasets, nonparametric methods offer a flexible alternative for estimating the overlapping coefficient Δ . Several studies have explored nonparametric approaches in this context.

Mulekar and Mishra (2000) employed jackknife and bootstrap techniques to construct confidence intervals for Δ without assuming any specific distributional form. Schmid and Schmidt (2006) proposed various nonparametric estimators and applied them to compare the income distributions of men and women in Germany.

The classical kernel method and its variants (see, Al-Kayead, 2011). have been central to nonparametric estimation of Δ and are the primary focus of this study. This traditional kernel approach has been widely used in earlier works (e.g., Clemons & Bradley, 2000; Clemons, 2001; Ridout & Linkie, 2009; Samawi et al., 2011; Eidous & Al-Talafheh, 2022; Eidous & Ananbeh, 2024), all of which estimated Δ based on two independent random samples. More recently, Almasri (2023) extended the traditional kernel method to estimate Δ for k independent samples, where $k \geq 2$.

In the present study, we aim to estimate Δ for $k \geq 2$ independent random samples with unknown probability density functions. Instead of using the traditional kernel method, we adopt a modified approach known as the multiplicative kernel method to achieve this objective.

Kernel methods and their adaptations, including location, scale, and fourth-order kernel estimators, have been widely used in other statistical applications. These include overlapping estimation (Al-Kharnobi, 2017; Suwaneh, 2024; Alshorman, 2024; Abu Al-Hayja`a, 2025), ecological analysis of line transect data (Eidous, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2009, 2011, 2012, 2015; Al Bassam & Eidous, 2018a, 2018b; Eidous & Al-Masri, 2006, 2010, Saeed, 2013; Abu-Sbeih, 2013; Almutlg, 2014; Abo Ehsaiyan, 2015; Mousa, 2015), reliability studies to estimate time-to-failure distributions and percentiles in degradation models (Al Haj Ebrahim et al., 2009;

Eidous et al., 2017; Ba Dakhn et al., 2017; Arif & Eidous, 2018; Al-Haj Ebrahim et al., 2021; Marie, 2025), and Goodness-of-Fit testing (Baklizi & Eidous, 2006, 2008; Alodat et al., 2022).

By extending nonparametric kernel techniques—specifically through the multiplicative kernel approach—this study contributes to a more general and adaptable framework for estimating Δ when dealing with multiple independent samples and unknown density functions.

1.4 Classical And Multiplicative Kernel Method

1.4.1 Classical kernel method

Let $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$ be a random sample from a continuous *pdf* $f(x)$. The traditional (classical) kernel density estimator of $f(x)$ is (Silverman, 1986)

$$\hat{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{j=1}^n K\left(\frac{x-X_j}{h}\right) \quad , \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (1.3)$$

where K is the kernel function and h is called a smoothing parameter (computed based on a sample $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$). The kernel function K is assumed to be positive, symmetric and satisfies,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(t)dt = 1 \quad , \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} tK(t)dt = 0 \quad , \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^2K(t)dt = c > 0 .$$

As noted by several authors (see Wand and Jones, 1995), under the assumptions that $h \rightarrow 0$ and $nh \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, the bias and variance of $\hat{f}(x)$ is,

$$\text{bias}(\hat{f}(x)) = h^2 f''(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^2 K(t) dt + o(h^2)$$

and

$$\text{var}(\hat{f}(x)) = \frac{f(x)}{nh} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(t)^2 dt + o(n^{-1}h^{-1}).$$

That is, the bias and variance convergence rates of $\hat{f}(x)$ are $O(h^2)$ and $O(n^{-1}h^{-1})$ as $h \rightarrow 0$ and $nh \rightarrow \infty$ respectively.

It is worth noting here that if the support for X is positive then the following estimator, which is called “reflection kernel estimator” (Silverman, 1986) can be used to estimate $f(x)$,

$$\hat{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{j=1}^n \left\{ K\left(\frac{x - X_j}{h}\right) + K\left(\frac{x + X_j}{h}\right) \right\}, \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (1.4)$$

To use the Estimator (1.3) or (1.4) in practice, we need to determine the kernel function K and to compute the value of h . The common choice of K is the standard normal *pdf*,

$$K(u) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}u^2}.$$

Also, the smoothing parameter can be computed by using the following rule, which is recommended by Silverman (1986),

$$h = 0.9 A n^{-1/5}$$

where

$$A = \min\{\text{standard deviation}, \text{interquartile range of } \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\}/1.34\}.$$

1.4.2. Multiplicative kernel method

Consider the same notations and assumptions in the previous subsection, the multiplicative kernel estimator of $f(x)$ is (Jones et al., 1995),

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{\hat{f}^*(x)}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^n \left[K\left(\frac{x - X_j}{b}\right) \right] [\hat{f}^*(X_j)]^{-1}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (1.5)$$

where K is the kernel function and b is the smoothing parameter of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is not necessarily the same as h .

The estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$ itself depends on another estimator, $\hat{f}^*(x)$, which can be any reasonable estimator for $f(x)$. It does not necessarily have to be good estimator and there is no need to waste a lot of time choosing it (Jones et al., 1995). It may be chosen as a non-parametric estimator (for example, a classical kernel), or it may be chosen as a parametric estimator (for example, normal distribution or half-normal distribution, etc.) considering the random variable range when choosing this estimator.

The asymptotic statistical properties of $\tilde{f}(x)$ were given by Jones et al. (1995).

While the bias convergence rate of the classical kernel estimator (1.3) is $O(h^2)$, it

is $O(b^4)$ for $\tilde{f}(x)$. The estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$ corrects the bias rate to be $O(b^4)$ instead of $O(h^2)$ as that of the classical kernel estimator. In addition, the rate of convergence for the variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is $O(n^{-1}b^{-1})$, the same as that of the classical kernel estimator, $\hat{f}(x)$.

It is known that the adaptations of the kernel estimator with $O(b^4)$ bias convergence rate are proportional to $n^{-1/9}$ instead of $n^{-1/5}$ as the classical kernel estimator. In this thesis, we used the following formula to compute the smoothing parameter b (see Swana, 2024 and Eidous and Talafhah, 2022),

$$b = 1.0834 S n^{-1/9} ,$$

where S is the sample standard deviation.

If the support of X is positive then the reflection multiplicative kernel estimator of $f(x)$ is,

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{\hat{f}^*(x)}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^n \left[K\left(\frac{x - X_j}{b}\right) + K\left(\frac{x + X_j}{b}\right) \right] [\hat{f}^*(X_j)]^{-1}, \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (1.6)$$

Again, $\hat{f}^*(x)$ is any reasonable (parametric or nonparametric) estimator for $f(x)$.

1.5 Objectives And Methodology

Our interest in this research focuses on three main points:

1. As the case in studies of Alsheyab (2023) and Almasri (2023), our interest will focus on dealing with the Weitzman coefficient as a measure of similarity or as an intersection area between k probability distributions and not just two

distributions, where $k \geq 2$. If $f_i(x), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ are k continuous probability density functions, then the generalized coefficient of Weitzman is given by the following formula,

$$\Delta_k = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx.$$

Note that the formula for the Weitzman coefficient in the case of two probability distributions (Equation 1.1) is a special case of the above formula when $k = 2$.

2. Use the nonparametric multiplicative kernel Estimator Equation (1.5) or (1.6) to estimate the generalized Weitzman coefficient assuming that there are k random samples.

Noting that Alsheyab, 2023; Almasri, 2023, studied the estimation of the generalized Weitzman coefficient. Alsheyab assumed that all of the k samples were taken from normal distributions with different means and also different variances, while Almasri assumed that all samples were taken from unknown distributions and then she used the classical kernel estimators (1.3) or (1.4) to estimate these unknown distributions.

3. In order to be able to conduct the estimation process of Δ_k , we will follow the same idea of Eidous & Talafha, 2022 and the other idea, which is proposed by Eidous & Ananbah, 2024. The first idea depends on writing the integral in the Weitzmann formula as an expected value of function(s) and then estimating the

expected value instead of estimating the integral itself. The basis of the other idea of Eidous & Ananbah, 2024 is to approximate the value of the integral in the Weitzmann formula using one of the methods of approximating integrals, such as the Simpson or Trapezoidal method, and then estimating the approximation we obtained instead of estimating the integral itself.

These two ideas were used independently by Alsheyyab (2023) and Almasri (2023). Accordingly, in this thesis, we achieved the following objectives:

- I. We used the multiplicative kernel estimators Estimators (1.5) and (1.6) to estimate the $f_i(x), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$.
- II. New numerous estimators for Δ_k are derived mathematically based on the same ideas of Eidous & Talafha (2022) and Eidous & Ananbah (2024a and 2024b).
- III. A simulation study is conducted to investigate and compare between the derived estimators themselves in case of $k = 3$. Also, we compared between them and the existing estimators of Δ_k that derived by Almasri (2023).

1.6 Organization Of The Thesis

In Chapter one, some concepts related to the topic of this thesis were discussed, and the relevant literature was also reviewed. In the Chapter two, new estimators for Δ_k were derived when k independent samples following unknown distributions were available. These estimators were obtained after writing the overlapping coefficient Δ_k as an expected value for a function or several functions and then

using the multiplicative kernel method to complete the estimation process. Two numerical examples were also provided in this chapter to illustrate how to apply and find the values of the different estimators. In the Chapter three, a new estimator for the overlapping coefficient Δ_k was derived, this time by finding an approximation of Δ_k using the trapezoidal method as a first stage. In the second stage, the multiplicative kernel method was used to find the final formulation of the proposed estimator. In Chapter four, we carried out an extensive simulation study, in order to examine the effectiveness of the proposed nonparametric estimators of Δ_k for $k = 3$. In addition, the classical kernel estimators were considered for the purpose of comparison.

The general and final conclusions were presented in Chapter five, in addition to some ideas related to future studies related to the topic of this thesis.

CHAPTER TWO

Expectation And Multiplicative Kernel Estimator For Weitzman

Coefficient Δ_k

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a number of estimators for the Weitzman overlapping coefficient,

$$\Delta_k = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\}dx. \quad (2.1)$$

using the multiplicative kernel method when there are k independent random samples (i.e. there are k populations) whose distribution formulas are unknown. In order to be able to use the multiplicative kernel method, we first wrote Δ_k as an expected value of a function or several functions (similar to the idea of Eidous and Talafha 2020, which was used to estimate Weitzman coefficient in the case of two samples), and then we presented several estimators for the resulting expectations instead of the integral itself. Two numerical examples are also provided which help in understanding the main ideas presented in this chapter.

2.2 Nonparametric Density Estimation Depends On k Samples

2.2.1 Classical kernel estimator

Let $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, X_{i3}, \dots, X_{in_i}$ be a random sample from a continuous *pdf* $f_i(x)$, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$. The classical kernel density estimator of $f_i(x)$ is (See Subsection 1.4.1),

$$\hat{f}_i(x) = \frac{1}{n_i h_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} K\left(\frac{x - X_{ij}}{h_i}\right), \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (2.2)$$

where K is the kernel function and h_i is the smoothing parameter (computed based on a sample $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, X_{i3}, \dots, X_{in_i}$).

If the support for X is positive then the reflection kernel estimator of $f_i(x)$ is,

$$\hat{f}_i(x) = \frac{1}{n_i h_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \left\{ K\left(\frac{x - X_{ij}}{h_i}\right) + K\left(\frac{x + X_{ij}}{h_i}\right) \right\}, \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (2.3)$$

The smoothing parameter h_i can be computed by using the following rule,

$$h_i = 0.9 A_i n_i^{-1/5}$$

where

$$A_i = \min\{\text{standard deviation}, \text{IQR}\{X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}\}/1.34\}.$$

2.2.2. Multiplicative kernel estimator

Consider the same notations and assumptions in the previous subsection, the multiplicative kernel estimator of $f_i(x)$ is (Jones et al., 1995),

$$\tilde{f}_i(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_i^*(x)}{n_i b_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \left[K \left(\frac{x - X_{ij}}{b_i} \right) \right] [\hat{f}_i^*(X_{ij})]^{-1}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (2.4)$$

The smoothing parameter b_i is computed by using the following rule (see Subsection, 1.4.2),

$$b_i = 1.0834 S_i n^{-1/9},$$

where S_i is the standard deviation of $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, X_{i3}, \dots, X_{in_i}, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

As mentioned in Subsection, 1.4.2, $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ is any reasonable (parametric or nonparametric) estimator for $f(x)$. In our simulation study given in Chapter 4, we considered two cases. The first one by taking $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ as the classical kernel estimator and the second case, we assumed that $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ is a parametric normal distribution or half-normal distribution depending on whether the support of X is the real number or it is the positive number.

If the support of X is positive then the reflection multiplicative kernel estimator of $f_i(x)$ is,

$$\tilde{f}_i(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_i^*(x)}{n_i b_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \left[K \left(\frac{x - X_{ij}}{b_i} \right) + K \left(\frac{x + X_{ij}}{b_i} \right) \right] [\hat{f}_i^*(X_{ij})]^{-1}, \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (2.5)$$

Again, $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ is any reasonable estimator for $f(x)$.

2.3 Nonparametric Density Estimation with Numerical Example

Numerical Example (1): One sample of size $n_1 = 20$ measurements is simulated from a standard normal distribution (i.e. $X_1 \sim N(0,1)$) with the exact $f_1(x)$,

$$f_1(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}x^2}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty.$$

The observed measurements $x_{1j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_1 = 20$ are:

\mathbf{x}_{1j} : 1.47 0.19 0.54 -0.08 -0.04 -0.12 -2.01 0.06 -0.47 1.11
 1.19 -0.80 0.14 1.69 0.16 -1.84 -0.77 0.90 -1.36 -1.12.

The mean, variance and interquartile range of the data are $\bar{X}_1 = -0.058$, $S_1^2 = 1.09423$ and $IQR = 1.505$ respectively. The parametric method to estimate $f_1(x)$ is,

$$\hat{f}_{Param}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(1.09423)}} e^{\frac{-1}{2(1.09423)}(x+0.058)^2}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty.$$

Note that, $\bar{X}_1 = -0.058$ and $S_1^2 = 1.09423$ are the maximum likelihood estimators of the mean and variance of normal distribution respectively. Our computation gives,

$$A_1 = \min \left\{ \sqrt{S_1^2}, \frac{IQR}{1.34} \right\} = \min \{ \sqrt{1.09423}, \frac{1.505}{1.34} \} = 1.046.$$

Therefore,

$$h_1 = 0.9 A_1 n_1^{-1/5} = 0.9 (1.046) 20^{-1/5} = 0.5171$$

and

$$b_1 = 1.0834 \sqrt{S_1^2} n_1^{-1/9} = 1.0834 (1.046) 20^{-1/9} = 0.8124$$

The classical kernel density estimator of $f_1(x)$ is,

$$\hat{f}_1(x) = \frac{1}{20(0.5171)} \sum_{j=1}^{20} K \left(\frac{x - x_{1j}}{0.5171} \right) \quad , \quad -\infty < x < \infty.$$

If K is a standard normal, then

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_1(x) &= \frac{1}{20(0.5171)\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{j=1}^{20} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - x_{1j}}{0.5171} \right)^2} \quad , \quad -\infty < x < \infty. \\ &= \frac{1}{20(0.5171)\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - 1.47}{0.5171} \right)^2} + e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - 0.19}{0.5171} \right)^2} + \dots + e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x + 1.12}{0.5171} \right)^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The multiplicative kernel estimate of $f_1(x)$ is,

$$\tilde{f}_1(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_1^*(x)}{20(0.8124)} \sum_{j=1}^{20} \left[K \left(\frac{x - x_{1j}}{0.8124} \right) \right] \left[\hat{f}_1^*(x_{1j}) \right]^{-1}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty$$

If the kernel function is taken to be a standard normal and if $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$ is taken to be the classical kernel, i.e. $\hat{f}_1^*(x) = \hat{f}_1(x)$ then the multiplicative kernel estimate is,

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{f}_1(x) &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{20} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-x_{1k}}{0.5171}\right)^2}}{20(0.8124)} \sum_{j=1}^{20} \left(\left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.8124}\right) \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^{20} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x_{1j}-x_{1k}}{0.5171}\right)^2} \right]^{-1} \right), \quad -\infty < x < \infty \\ &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{20} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-x_{1k}}{0.5171}\right)^2}}{20(0.8124)\sqrt{2}\pi} \sum_{j=1}^{20} \left(\left[e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.8124}\right)^2} \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^{20} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x_{1j}-x_{1k}}{0.5171}\right)^2} \right]^{-1} \right).\end{aligned}$$

If $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$ is taken to be the parametric normal distribution $\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$, which is given above, i.e $\hat{f}_1^*(x) = \hat{f}_{Param}(x)$ then the multiplicative kernel estimate is,

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{f}_1^*(x) &= \frac{e^{-\frac{(x+0.058)^2}{2(1.09423)}}}{20(0.8124)} \sum_{j=1}^{20} \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.8124}\right) \right] e^{\frac{(x_{1j}+0.058)^2}{2(1.09423)}}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty \\ &= \frac{e^{-\frac{(x+0.058)^2}{2(1.09423)}}}{20(0.8124)\sqrt{2}\pi} \sum_{j=1}^{20} \left(\left[e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.8124}\right)^2} \right] e^{\frac{(x_{1j}+0.058)^2}{2(1.09423)}} \right).\end{aligned}$$

For some specific values of x , Table (2.1) below gives the exact values of $f_1(x) = N(0, 1)$, the parametric estimates $\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$, the classical kernel estimates $\hat{f}_1(x)$, the multiplicative kernel with classical kernel estimator, $\tilde{f}_1(x)$ and the multiplicative kernel with normal distribution estimator, $\tilde{f}_1^*(x)$. In addition, the curves of the various estimates function together with the curve of the exact function are given in Figure 2.1.

Table (2.1)

The exact values of $f_1(x)$ and the estimated values of $\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$, $\hat{f}_1(x)$, $\tilde{f}_1(x)$ and $\tilde{f}_1^*(x)$ for the values $x = -3.6 (0.8) 3.6$.

x	$f_1(x)$	$\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$	$\hat{f}_1(x)$	$\tilde{f}_1(x)$	$\tilde{f}_1^*(x)$
-3.6	0.000612	0.001235	0.000463	0.000027	0.000105
-2.8	0.007916	0.012283	0.019931	0.005896	0.005124
-2.	0.053991	0.068067	0.107867	0.074856	0.060275
-1.2	0.194186	0.210159	0.191167	0.179840	0.214006
-0.4	0.368270	0.361531	0.314634	0.322560	0.356252
0.0	0.398942	0.380793	0.355649	0.368684	0.380243
0.4	0.368270	0.346521	0.320667	0.327428	0.353857
1.2	0.194186	0.185054	0.209193	0.181782	0.180970
2.	0.053991	0.055063	0.080142	0.040191	0.034175
2.8	0.007916	0.009128	0.005801	0.000855	0.001762
3.6	0.000612	0.000843	0.000051	9.68×10^{-7}	0.000022

a) $N(0, 1)$ and $\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$

b) $N(0, 1)$ and $\hat{f}_1(x)$

c) $N(0, 1)$ and $\tilde{f}_1(x)$

d) $N(0, 1)$ and $\tilde{f}_{1^*}(x)$

Figure (2.1) The curve of exact $f_1(x) = N(0, 1)$ (solid) with a) $\hat{f}_{Param}(x)$ (dashed), b) $\hat{f}_1(x)$ (dashed), c) $\tilde{f}_1(x)$ (dashed) and d) $\tilde{f}_{1^*}(x)$ (dashed).

2.4 Modeling Of Δ_3 As Expectation

The symbol Δ_3 (i.e. Δ_k in 2.1 with $k = 3$) represents the Weitzman overlapping coefficient between three probability density functions $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ and $f_3(x)$.

That is,

$$\Delta_3 = \int \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x)\} dx. \quad (2.6)$$

In this section, we demonstrate how to express the parameter Δ_3 as expected value of some functions.

Assume that X_1, X_2, X_3 are three independent continuous random variables from unknown probability density functions $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$, $f_3(x)$ respectively.

Let $W_1(X_1) = \min\{f_1(X_1), f_2(X_1), f_3(X_1)\}/f_1(X_1)$ be a function of a random variable X_1 and let $\Delta_3(X_1) = E(W_1(X_1))$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_3(X_1) &= E(W_1(X_1)) \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min\{f_1(x_1), f_2(x_1), f_3(x_1)\}}{f_1(x_1)} f_1(x_1) dx_1 \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x_1), f_2(x_1), f_3(x_1)\} dx_1 \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x)\} dx \\ &= \Delta_3. \end{aligned}$$

Also, let $W_2(X_2) = \min \{f_1(X_2), f_2(X_2), f_3(X_2)\} / f_2(X_2)$ be a function of a random variable X_2 and let $\Delta_3(X_2) = E(W_2(X_2))$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_3(X_2) &= E(W_2(X_2)) \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min \{f_1(x_2), f_2(x_2), f_3(x_2)\}}{f_2(x_2)} f_2(x_2) dx_2 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x_2), f_2(x_2), f_3(x_2)\} dx_2 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x)\} dx \\
 &= \Delta_3 .
 \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, and if we define $W_3(X_3) = \min \{f_1(X_3), f_2(X_3), f_3(X_3)\} / f_3(X_3)$ as a function of a random variable X_3 then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_3(X_3) &= E(W_3(X_3)) \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min \{f_1(x_3), f_2(x_3), f_3(x_3)\}}{f_3(x_3)} f_3(x_3) dx_3 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x_3), f_2(x_3), f_3(x_3)\} dx_3 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x)\} dx \\
 &= \Delta_3 .
 \end{aligned}$$

In the above derivation, we showed that the parameter Δ_3 can be expressed or modeling as an expected value of a function $W_1(X_1)$, $W_2(X_2)$ or $W_3(X_3)$, which indicates that $\Delta_3(X_1) = E(W_1(X_1))$, $\Delta_3(X_2) = E(W_2(X_2))$ and $\Delta_3(X_3) = E(W_3(X_3))$ and therefore, $\Delta_3 = \Delta_3(X_1) = \Delta_3(X_2) = \Delta_3(X_3)$. Furthermore, Δ_3 can be expressed as the average of any two of $\Delta_3(X_1)$, $\Delta_3(X_2)$ and $\Delta_3(X_3)$ or even the average of all of them. Let,

$$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2) = \frac{\Delta_3(X_1) + \Delta_3(X_2)}{2},$$

$$\Delta_3(X_1, X_3) = \frac{\Delta_3(X_1) + \Delta_3(X_3)}{2},$$

$$\Delta_3(X_2, X_3) = \frac{\Delta_3(X_2) + \Delta_3(X_3)}{2}$$

and

$$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{\Delta_3(X_1) + \Delta_3(X_2) + \Delta_3(X_3)}{3}$$

then,

$$\Delta_3 = \Delta_3(X_1, X_2) = \Delta_3(X_1, X_3) = \Delta_3(X_2, X_3) = \Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3).$$

In conclusion, $\Delta_3 = \Delta_3(X_1) = \Delta_3(X_2) = \Delta_3(X_3) = \Delta_3(X_1, X_2) = \Delta_3(X_1, X_3) = \Delta_3(X_2, X_3) = \Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and estimating any of them means estimating the others.

2.5 Estimation Of Δ_3

The main goal in this section is to illustrate how we can estimate Δ_3 based on three independent random samples:

Let X_1, X_2, X_3 be three independent continuous random variables from $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$, $f_3(x)$ respectively. Also, let

$X_{11}, X_{12}, \dots, X_{1n_1}$ is a random sample of size n_1 from $f_1(x)$

$X_{21}, X_{22}, \dots, X_{2n_2}$ is a random sample of size n_2 from $f_2(x)$

$X_{31}, X_{32}, \dots, X_{3n_3}$ is a random sample of size n_3 from $f_3(x)$.

According to these three samples, the estimate of Δ_3 can be obtained by estimating any of the parameters $\Delta_3(X_1)$, $\Delta_3(X_2)$, $\Delta_3(X_3)$ and thus any of the parameters $\Delta_3(X_1, X_2)$, $\Delta_3(X_1, X_3)$, $\Delta_3(X_2, X_3)$ and $\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ because they are all equal and each of them is equal to the parameter Δ_3 .

Prior to beginning the Δ_3 estimate method, let us go back to the "Method of Moments" a popular statistical estimating technique. If $w(U)$ is a function of a random variable U , then by using this method, we estimate the mean of $w(U)$ by its sample counterpart. That is, $E(w(U))$ is estimated by the mean of $w(U_1)$, $w(U_2), \dots, w(U_m)$, where U_1, U_2, \dots, U_m is a random sample of size m from the same *pdf* of U .

Now, since $\Delta_3 = \Delta_3(X_1)$, which is the expected value (mean) of $W_1(X_1) = \min \{f_1(X_1), f_2(X_1), f_3(X_1)\}/f_1(X_1)$ then $\Delta_3(X_1)$ (and then Δ_3) is estimated by the average of $\min \{f_1(X_{1j}), f_2(X_{1j}), f_3(X_{1j})\}/f_1(X_{1j})$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_1$. Because f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are unknown, then we estimate them by using the multiplicative kernel method. Their corresponding multiplicative kernel estimators are \tilde{f}_1 , \tilde{f}_2 and \tilde{f}_3 , which are given by equations (2.4) and (2.5). Therefore, the first proposed estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1)$ of Δ_3 (or $\Delta_3(X_1)$) is the mean of the following quantities,

$$\frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{1j})\}}{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j})}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n_1.$$

That is,

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{1j})\}}{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j})}.$$

Using the same technique as above, we can derive the following proposed estimators for Δ_3 ,

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2) = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{2j}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{2j}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{2j})\}}{\tilde{f}_2(X_{2j})}$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3) = \frac{1}{n_3} \sum_{j=1}^{n_3} \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{3j}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{3j}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{3j})\}}{\tilde{f}_3(X_{3j})}$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2) = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2))$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_3) = \frac{1}{2}(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3))$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2, X_3) = \frac{1}{2}(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3))$$

and

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{1}{3}(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3))$$

2.6 Numerical Example

Consider the following three independent samples, which are simulated from $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 1.2)$ and $N(0.5, 2.25)$ respectively with sizes 5, 3 and 6 as follows:

Sample 1: -0.06 -1.31 1.28 -0.72 0.63

Sample 2: 1.05 -1.18 0.02

Sample 3: -0.35 0.95 0.45 1.17 2.51 -1.88

The measurements of these three samples corresponds the following notations:

Sample 1: x_{11} x_{12} x_{13} x_{14} x_{15}

Sample 2: x_{21} x_{22} x_{23}

Sample 3: x_{31} x_{32} x_{33} x_{34} x_{35} x_{36}

The exact value of Δ_3 is,

$$\Delta_3 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{N(0, 1), N(0, 1.2), N(0.5, 2.25)\}dx = 0.760875$$

The shaded area in Figure 2.2 represents the overlapping coefficient Δ_3 . To estimate Δ_3 using the technique in Section (2.5), we first need to find the multiplicative kernel estimate based on each of the three samples mentioned above. For comparison purpose, the corresponding classical kernel estimate was also found. The mean, variance and interquartile (IQR) range were calculated for each sample and are shown in Table 2.2. In addition, in the same table, the values of the smoothing parameters h (for classical kernel) and b (for multiplicative kernel) were given based on each sample separately.

Based on these calculations, the classical kernel estimates, the multiplicative kernel estimate with a classical kernel for $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$ and the multiplicative kernel estimate with a normal distribution for $\tilde{f}_1^*(x)$ become as follows,

Let $N(\mu, \sigma^2; u)$ be the normal *pdf* at a point u with mean μ and variance σ^2

For Sample 1: $-\infty < x < \infty$

$$\hat{f}_1(x) = \frac{1}{5(0.674)} \sum_{j=1}^5 K\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.674}\right),$$

$$\tilde{f}_1(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_1(x)}{5(0.936)} \sum_{j=1}^5 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.936}\right) \right] \left[\hat{f}_1(x_{1j}) \right]^{-1},$$

$$\tilde{f}_1^*(x) = \frac{N(-0.036, 1.067; x)}{5(0.936)} \sum_{j=1}^5 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{1j}}{0.936}\right) \right] [N(-0.036, 1.067; x_{1j})]^{-1}$$

For Sample 2: $-\infty < x < \infty$

$$\hat{f}_2(x) = \frac{1}{3(0.806)} \sum_{j=1}^3 K\left(\frac{x-x_{2j}}{0.806}\right),$$

$$\tilde{f}_2(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_2(x)}{3(1.07)} \sum_{j=1}^3 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{2j}}{1.07}\right) \right] [\hat{f}_2(x_{2j})]^{-1},$$

$$\tilde{f}_2^*(x) = \frac{N(-0.037, 1.246; x)}{3(1.07)} \sum_{j=1}^3 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{2j}}{1.07}\right) \right] [N(-0.037, 1.246; x_{2j})]^{-1}$$

For Sample 3: $-\infty < x < \infty$

$$\hat{f}_3(x) = \frac{1}{6(0.713)} \sum_{j=1}^6 K\left(\frac{x-x_{3j}}{0.713}\right),$$

$$\tilde{f}_3(x) = \frac{\hat{f}_3(x)}{3(1.322)} \sum_{j=1}^6 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{3j}}{1.322}\right) \right] [\hat{f}_3(x_{3j})]^{-1},$$

$$\tilde{f}_3^*(x) = \frac{N(0.475, 2.215; x)}{6(1.322)} \sum_{j=1}^6 \left[K\left(\frac{x-x_{3j}}{1.322}\right) \right] [N(0.475, 2.215; x_{3j})]^{-1}.$$

Now, the first multiplicative kernel estimate of Δ_3 is,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) &= \frac{1}{5} \sum_{j=1}^5 \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{1j}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{1j})\}}{\tilde{f}_1(X_{1j})} \\ &= \frac{1}{5} \left(\frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(-.06), \tilde{f}_2(-0.06), \tilde{f}_3(-0.06)\}}{\tilde{f}_1(-0.06)} + \dots + \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(0.63), \tilde{f}_2(0.63), \tilde{f}_3(0.63)\}}{\tilde{f}_1(0.63)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 0.711 \quad (\text{see Table 2.3 below})$$

The other two estimators $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3)$ can be computed in the same way using the measurements of Sample 2 and Sample 3 respectively. Also, the classical kernel estimates and the second multiplicative kernel estimates can be computed using the same technique. Table (2.3) gives the various estimates of Δ_3 . Based on the entries of this table, we can compute $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2)$, $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_3)$, $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_2, X_3)$ and $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ for the classical kernel estimates and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2)$, $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_3)$, $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2, X_3)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ for the multiplicative kernel estimates. For example, the multiplicative kernel estimate (with normal distribution for $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$) $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{0.782 + 0.826 + 0.702}{3} = 0.77.$$

Figure (2.2). The shaded area represents the exact Δ_3 .

Table (2.2). The mean, variance, interquartile range (IQ), smoothing parameters h and b based on the above three samples.

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Mean	-0.036	-0.037	0.475
Variance	1.067	1.246	2.215
IQR	1.660	1.673	1.520
h	0.674	0.806	0.713
b	0.936	1.070	1.322

Table (2.3). Various estimators of $\Delta_3(X_i), i = 1, 2, 3$ based on the above three samples.

Method	$\Delta_3(X_1)$	$\Delta_3(X_2)$	$\Delta_3(X_3)$
classical kernel estimate	0.739	0.762	0.827
Multiplicative kernel estimate with classical kernel for $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$	0.711	0.739	0.731
Multiplicative kernel estimate with normal distribution for $\hat{f}_1^*(x)$	0.782	0.826	0.702

2.7 Modeling The General Δ_k As Expectation

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k be independent continuous random variables with unknown pdfs $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)$ respectively. Formula (2.1) gives the Weitzman coefficient Δ_k depending on these k random variables. As previously said, finding the integral of Δ_k itself is a really difficult task, making estimating Δ_k a difficult task. As a result, the goal of this section is to express Δ_k as the expected value of a function or some functions. After that, we will estimate the expected value rather than the integral itself that arises in the formula of Δ_k .

Let $\min \{f_1(X_1), f_2(X_1), \dots, f_k(X_1)\} / f_1(X_1)$ be a function of a random variable X_1 and let $\Delta_k(X_1) = E \left(\frac{\min \{f_1(X_1), f_2(X_1), \dots, f_k(X_1)\}}{f_1(X_1)} \right)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_k(X_1) &= E \left(\frac{\min \{f_1(X_1), f_2(X_1), \dots, f_k(X_1)\}}{f_1(X_1)} \right) \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min \{f_1(x_1), f_2(x_1), \dots, f_k(x_1)\}}{f_1(x_1)} f_1(x_1) dx_1 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x_1), f_2(x_1), \dots, f_k(x_1)\} dx_1 \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx \\
 &= \Delta_k .
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

Other functions of X_2, X_3, \dots, X_k can be defined similarly (see also, section, 2.4).

In general, let $\min\{f_1(X_i), f_2(X_i), \dots, f_k(X_i)\}/f_i(X_i)$ to be a function of a random variable X_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ and let

$$\Delta_k(X_i) = E \left(\frac{\min\{f_1(X_i), f_2(X_i), \dots, f_k(X_i)\}}{f_i(X_i)} \right)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_k(X_i) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min\{f_1(x_i), f_2(x_i), \dots, f_k(x_i)\}}{f_i(x_i)} f_i(x_i) dx_i \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x_i), f_2(x_i), \dots, f_k(x_i)\} dx_i \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx \\ &= \Delta_k. \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

The above-mentioned derivations illustrate how to express the parameter Δ_k as expected value of some functions and show that,

$$\Delta_k(X_1) = \Delta_k(X_2) = \Delta_k(X_3) = \dots = \Delta_k(X_k) = \Delta_k.$$

That is,

$$\Delta_k = \Delta_k(X_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

Accordingly, to estimate Δ_k it is possible to estimate any of $\Delta_k(X_1)$, $\Delta_k(X_2)$, $\Delta_k(X_3)$, ..., $\Delta_k(X_k)$ and the reverse is also true. It is worthwhile to mention here that Δ_k can be expressed as the average of two, three, four, ..., up to k terms of $\Delta_k(X_1)$, $\Delta_k(X_2)$, $\Delta_k(X_3)$, ..., $\Delta_k(X_k)$. For example, it is possible to re-write Δ_k as the average of the previous quantities as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_k(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k) &= \frac{1}{k} (\Delta_k(X_1) + \Delta_k(X_2) + \Delta_k(X_3) + \dots + \Delta_k(X_k)) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \Delta_k(X_i) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k E \left(\frac{\min\{f_1(X_i), f_2(X_i), \dots, f_k(X_i)\}}{f_i(X_i)} \right), \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} k \Delta_k = \Delta_k.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.8 Estimation Of Δ_k

Let $X_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ be independent continuous random variables from $f_i(x), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ respectively. Assume that $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in_i}$ is a random sample from $f_i(x), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, where the k samples are independent. These k samples can be described as given below (see also, Section 2.5):

$X_{11}, X_{12}, \dots, X_{1n_1}$ is a random sample of size n_1 from $f_1(x)$

$X_{21}, X_{22}, \dots, X_{2n_2}$ is a random sample of size n_2 from $f_2(x)$

$$= \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \frac{1}{n_i} \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{ij}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{ij}), \dots, \tilde{f}_k(X_{ij})\}}{\tilde{f}_i(X_{ij})}.$$

The finite statistical properties of the different estimators derived in this chapter, in the case $k = 3$, were investigated and studied in Chapter 4.

CHAPTER THREE

Approximation And Multiplicative Kernel Estimator Of Δ_k

3.1 Introduction

This chapter proposed a new estimator for the Weitzman overlapping coefficient Δ_k . Initially, we approximate the integral that appears in the Δ_k formula (2.1) and then estimate the resulting approximation rather than the integral itself using the multiplicative kernel method. The two cases, when the range of the random variables of interest is all real numbers and when the range is the positive real numbers are considered and discussed in details.

3.2 Trapezoidal Rule

Trapezoidal rule is a technique for approximating certain finite integrals of continuous function $f(x)$ (Chapra and Canale, 2014). Let $g(x)$ be continuous on $[a, b]$, which is divided into r equal-sized subintervals, then the trapezoidal rule for approximating $\int_a^b g(x)dx$ is,

$$\int_a^b g(x)dx = \frac{\Delta x}{2} [g(a) + 2g(x_1) + 2g(x_2) \dots + 2g(x_{r-1}) + g(b)] ,$$

where $\Delta x = \frac{b-a}{r}$, a and b are finite real numbers, and r is a positive integer number.

The maximum absolute error (MAE) of the trapezoidal rule is,

$$|MAE| \leq \left| \frac{M(b-a)^3}{12r^2} \right| ,$$

where, M is the maximum value of $|g''(c)|$, $c \in [a, b]$.

3.3 Approximation And Estimation Of Δ_k

Assume that X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k are continuous random variables with unknown *pdfs* $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)$ respectively, where the random variables are defined on $(-\infty, \infty)$ or on $(0, \infty)$.

If $x \in (-\infty, \infty)$, then the Weitzman Δ_k is,

$$\Delta_k = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx.$$

If $x \in (0, \infty)$, then the Weitzman Δ_k is,

$$\Delta_k = \int_0^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx.$$

Finding the values of the above integrals, in general, is not an easy task, if not impossible. Even if the formulas of the distributions appearing in these integrals are known and in the presence of unknown parameters, the problem remains not

easy because it requires determining the points of intersection between the different distributions and then trying to find the value of the integral. The issue becomes more difficult and complicated if the distribution formulas are not known. In order to overcome this problem, our main interest here is to approximate these integrals using the trapezoidal rule and then perform the estimation process using the multiplicative kernel method for the obtained approximation. To be able to apply the trapezoidal rule, it is necessary that the bounds of integral be finite. For this reason, we first need an appropriate transformation so that the limits of integrals become finite values, and then apply the trapezoidal rule.

3.3.1 Approximation Δ_k with support $(-\infty, \infty)$

Assume that the support of a random variable X is $(-\infty, \infty)$ and assume that $q = u(x)$ is a continuous increasing or decreasing function in x such that $u(-\infty) = c$ and $u(\infty) = d$, where c and d are finite real numbers. Then, we can transform the infinite integral bounds into finite bounds using this general transformation. In this instance,

$$x = u^{-1}(q) (= v(q), \text{ say})$$

and

$$dx = v'(q) dq .$$

Therefore, Δ_k becomes,

$$\Delta_k = \int_c^d \min\{f_1(v(q)), f_2(v(q)), \dots, f_k(v(q))\} v'(q) dq.$$

Even so, and to be more exact, let $R_L(x)$ be the cumulative distribution function of a random variable L , where L has a generalized logistic distribution with a cumulative distribution function given by,

$$R_L(x) = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + e^x)^\theta}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad \theta > 0.$$

and probability density function (*pdf*),

$$r_L(x) = \frac{\theta e^x}{(1 + e^x)^{\theta+1}}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad \theta > 0$$

Here, the parameter θ can be selected arbitrary or can be estimated depends on a specific random sample. If L_1, L_2, \dots, L_m is a random sample from $r_L(x)$ then the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of θ is,

$$\hat{\theta} = m / \sum_{i=1}^m \ln(1 + e^{L_i}).$$

Now, we take the transformation to be $u = R_L(x)$, so the inverse transformation is,

$$x = \ln((1 - u)^{-1/\theta} - 1).$$

Since u is a number between 0 and 1 then we can write the inverse transformation as follows,

$$x = \ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)$$

and

$$\left| \frac{dx}{du} \right| = \frac{1}{\theta u(1 - u^{1/\theta})}.$$

Note that,

$$R_L(-\infty) = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-\infty})^\theta} = 1 - 1 = 0$$

and

$$R_L(\infty) = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + e^\infty)^\theta} = 1 - 0 = 1.$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta_k = - \int_0^1 \frac{\min\{f_1(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), f_2(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), \dots, f_k(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1))\}}{\theta u(1 - u^{1/\theta})} du.$$

Now, let

$$g(u) = \frac{\min\{f_1(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), f_2(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), \dots, f_k(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1))\}}{\theta u(1 - u^{1/\theta})}$$

then

$$\Delta_k = \int_0^1 g(u) du.$$

The approximation of $\Delta_k = \int_0^1 g(u) du$ by using the trapezoidal rule is,

$$\Delta_k \cong \frac{1}{2r} \left[g(0) + 2g\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) + 2g\left(\frac{2}{r}\right) \dots + 2g\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right) + g(1) \right], \quad (3.1)$$

where r is the number of partitions of the interval $[0, 1]$.

3.3.2 Estimation Δ_k with Support $(-\infty, \infty)$

Assume that X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k are k independent continuous random variables from unknown *pdfs* $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)$ respectively, where the support of each random variable is $(-\infty, \infty)$. If the following k independent samples are drawn from the corresponding density as described below,

$X_{11}, X_{12}, \dots, X_{1n_1}$ is a random sample of size n_1 from unknown $f_1(x)$

$X_{21}, X_{22}, \dots, X_{2n_2}$ is a random sample of size n_2 from unknown $f_2(x)$

$\vdots \qquad \qquad \qquad \vdots \qquad \qquad \qquad \vdots$

$X_{k1}, X_{k2}, \dots, X_{kn_k}$ is a random sample of size n_k from unknown $f_k(x)$

Our main aim now is to estimate Δ_k by using the multiplicative kernel method.

Based on the above random samples we can estimate the approximate formula

(3.1) of Δ_k instead of estimating its exact value.

Let $\tilde{f}_i(x)$ be the multiplicative kernel estimator (see Subsection, 2.2.2) of $f_i(x)$, $i =$

$1, 2, \dots, k$ and let

$$\tilde{g}(u) = \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), \tilde{f}_2(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1)), \dots, \tilde{f}_k(\ln((1/u)^{1/\theta} - 1))\}}{\theta u(1 - u^{1/\theta})}$$

be the estimator of $g(u)$, which is defined in the previous Subsection. Then the

new proposed multiplicative kernel estimator of Δ_k is,

$$\tilde{\Delta}_k = \frac{1}{2r} \left[\tilde{g}(0) + 2\tilde{g}\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) + 2\tilde{g}\left(\frac{2}{r}\right) + \dots + 2\tilde{g}\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right) + \tilde{g}(1) \right] \quad (3.2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j=1}^{r-1} \tilde{g} \left(\frac{j}{r} \right).$$

The two quantities $\tilde{g}(0)$ and $\tilde{g}(1)$ are the estimators for $g(0)$ and $g(1)$ respectively. Because $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} g(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} g(t) = 0$ then the corresponding estimators $\tilde{g}(0)$ and $\tilde{g}(1)$ will disappeared in formula (3.2).

It is important to note here that if $\hat{f}_i(x)$ is the classical kernel estimator of $f_i(x)$ and if this estimator is used instead of $\tilde{f}_i(x)$ in $\tilde{g}(u)$ then we obtain the classical kernel estimator $\hat{g}(u)$ of $g(u)$. In addition, if $\hat{g}(u)$ is used instead of \tilde{g} in $\tilde{\Delta}_k$ then we obtained the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_k$ of Δ_k . In other words, $\hat{\Delta}_k$ is the same as $\tilde{\Delta}_k$, with the only difference being that $\hat{\Delta}_k$ used $\hat{f}_i(x)$ instead of $\tilde{f}_i(x)$ that is used in $\tilde{\Delta}_k$.

The finite statistical properties of $\hat{\Delta}_k$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_k$ are investigated in Chapter 4, in which an extensive simulation study is achieved. In that study, two arbitrary values for the parameter θ ($\theta = 1, 2$) are taken and another value is taken based the simulated data by using the MLE of θ .

3.4 Approximation And Estimation of Δ_k For Support $(0, \infty)$

Using the same notations as in the previous section, if the support of all random variables is $(0, \infty)$, then to approximate

$$\Delta_k = \int_0^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx.$$

by using the trapezoidal rule, we need to determine the appropriate transformation to change the limits of integration from infinite to finite. Here we propose the following transformation, which is the cumulative exponential distribution that defined over positive values,

$$R_L(x) = 1 - e^{-x/\theta}, \quad 0 < x < \infty, \quad \theta > 0$$

where θ is unknown parameters. In this case, the interested transformation is $u = 1 - e^{-x/\theta}$ with inverse transformation $x = -\theta \ln(1 - u)$. This gives,

$$dx = \frac{\theta}{(1 - u)} du.$$

Because $R_L(0) = 1 - e^{-0/\theta} = 0$ and $R_L(\infty) = 1 - e^{-\infty/\theta} = 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_k &= \int_0^{\infty} \min\{f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)\} dx \\ &= \int_0^1 \frac{\theta \min\{f_1(-\theta \ln u), f_2(-\theta \ln u), \dots, f_k(-\theta \ln u)\}}{u} du. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$g_1(u) = \frac{\theta \min\{f_1(-\theta \ln u), f_2(-\theta \ln u), \dots, f_k(-\theta \ln u)\}}{u}$$

then

$$\Delta_k = \int_0^1 g_1(u) du$$

and its approximation by using the trapezoidal rule is,

$$\Delta_k \cong \frac{1}{2r} \left[g_1(0) + 2g_1\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) + 2g_1\left(\frac{2}{r}\right) + \cdots + 2g_1\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right) + g_1(1) \right].$$

where r is the number of partitions of the interval $[0, 1]$.

Let $\tilde{f}_i(x)$ be the reflection multiplicative kernel estimator of $f_i(x)$, equation (2.5)

then the multiplicative kernel estimator of is,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Delta}_k &= \frac{1}{2r} \left[\tilde{g}_1(0) + 2\tilde{g}_1\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) + 2\tilde{g}_1\left(\frac{2}{r}\right) + \cdots + 2\tilde{g}_1\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right) + \hat{g}_1(1) \right] \quad (3.2) \\ &= \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j=1}^{r-1} \tilde{g}_1\left(\frac{j}{r}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\tilde{g}_1(u) = \frac{\theta \min\{\tilde{f}_1(-\theta \ln u), \tilde{f}_2(-\theta \ln u), \dots, \tilde{f}_k(-\theta \ln u)\}}{u}.$$

The simulation study of Chapter 4 considers the estimator (3.2) to investigate its statistical properties and to compare its performance with the corresponding classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_k$.

CHAPTER FOUR

Simulations Study And Numerical Results

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we carry out a rather extensive simulation study, in order to examine the effectiveness of the proposed nonparametric estimators for the Weitzman overlapping coefficient. The finite statistical properties of the proposed estimators were compared with the corresponding ones using the classical kernel method at $k = 3$.

4.2 Description Of Simulated Study

Taking the value of $k = 3$, we simulated the data from four families of distributions, in which two families defined on $(-\infty, \infty)$ values and the other two families defined on $(0, \infty)$. For each family of distributions, we took four cases depending on the choice of the corresponding parameter(s). Even if the distribution parameters appear to be randomly chosen, we keep in mind that they should be selected to vary the values of Δ_3 between 0 and 1. In other words, the parameters were chosen such that we included large values for Δ_3 , medium and above half, medium and less than half, in addition to a small value for Δ_3 . Accordingly, we

have 16 possible scenarios for drawing three independent samples from each scenario. These possible scenarios are given in Table (4.1), along with the exact value of Δ_3 for each scenario. In addition, each scenario is represented graphically in Figure 4.1. For each case of the 16 scenarios, the three independent samples were generated 1000 times for the sample sizes $(n_1, n_2, n_3) = (20, 20, 20)$ and $(50, 100, 150)$. Mathematica Version 13 was used in all computations and graphs. The family of distributions chosen for this simulation study includes the normal, extreme, Weibull and half normal distributions, note that the support of the first two distributions is $(-\infty, \infty)$, while the support of the last two distributions is $(0, \infty)$.

The following are the pdfs for these distribution:

- Extreme value distribution, $EX(\mu, \alpha)$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\alpha} e^{\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\alpha} - e^{\frac{x-\mu}{\alpha}}\right)}, \quad \alpha > 0, x \in \mathcal{R}$$

- Normal distribution, $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad x \in \mathcal{R}, \mu \in \mathcal{R}, \sigma^2 > 0$$

- Weibull distribution, $W(\alpha, \beta)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-(x/\alpha)^\beta}, \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0$$

- Half Normal distribution, $\mathcal{HN}(\theta)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{2\theta e^{-\frac{x^2\theta^2}{\pi}}}{\pi}, \quad x > 0, \quad \theta > 0$$

Table (4.1). The simulated three distributions $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ and $f_3(x)$ and the corresponding exact value of the overlapping coefficient Δ_3 .

Distribution	$f_1(x)$	$f_2(x)$	$f_3(x)$	Δ_3
Case 1: Extreme	EX(0,1)	EX(0,1.2)	EX(0.2,1.2)	0.8844
Case 2: Extreme	EX(0,1)	EX(1,2)	EX(0.4,1.4)	0.6397
Case 3: Extreme	EX(-1.5,1)	EX(1.5,2)	EX(0,1)	0.3108
Case 4: Extreme	EX(0.5,0.2)	EX(-1.8,1)	EX(1.8,1)	0.0878
Case 5: Normal	N(-0.1,1)	N(0.1,1)	N(0.3,1)	0.8415
Case 6: Normal	N(-0.5,1)	N(0,1)	N(0.5,1)	0.6171
Case 7: Normal	N(0,1)	N(1,0.8)	N(1.5,2)	0.4235
Case 8: Normal	N(-1,0.2)	N(0,1)	N(1,1.2)	0.0965
Case 9: Weibull	W(2,2)	W(2,2.2)	W(2,2.2)	0.8975
Case 10: Weibull	W(2,2.5)	W(3,3)	W(3,3.5)	0.6644
Case 11: Weibull	W(1.5,1)	W(1.5,3)	W(1,1)	0.4429
Case 12: Weibull	W(8,3)	W(3,5)	W(6,2)	0.1089
Case13: Half Normal	$\mathcal{HN}(1)$	$\mathcal{HN}(1.15)$	$\mathcal{HN}(1.25)$	0.8925
Case14: Half Normal	$\mathcal{HN}(1.5)$	$\mathcal{HN}(1.75)$	$\mathcal{HN}(3.5)$	0.6127
Case15: Half Normal	$\mathcal{HN}(1)$	$\mathcal{HN}(3.5)$	$\mathcal{HN}(5)$	0.3529
Case16: Half Normal	$\mathcal{HN}(0.3)$	$\mathcal{HN}(4)$	$\mathcal{HN}(0.5)$	0.1584

Case 1

Case 2

Case 3

Case 4

Case 5

Case 6

Case 7

Case 8

Figure (4.1). The graphs of 16 scenarios of Δ_3 as $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ and $f_3(x)$ given in Table (4.1).

4.3 Estimators Under Study

In this section, we would like to study and investigate the properties of the estimators developed and proposed in this thesis. To make the picture clearer, the corresponding estimators, which depend on the classical kernel method and were proposed by Almasri (2023) are also considered. Because we took the value of $k = 3$ in our simulation study, the estimators of Δ_3 under study can be summarized as follows:

The multiplicative kernel estimators (see Section, 2.5):

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_i) = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \frac{\min\{\tilde{f}_1(X_{ij}), \tilde{f}_2(X_{ij}), \tilde{f}_3(X_{ij})\}}{\tilde{f}_i(X_{ij})}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

and

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{1}{3} \left(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2) + \tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3) \right)$$

where $\tilde{f}_i(t)$ is the multiplicative kernel estimator based on sample i at point t . In this simulation study, the function $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ that arises in the formula of the multiplicative kernel estimator is selected to be $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ if the density support is $(-\infty, \infty)$ and $\mathcal{HN}(\theta)$ if the density support is $(0, \infty)$, where μ and σ^2 are estimated from their corresponding data set and using the maximum likelihood method. The nonparametric classical kernel method was also used to determine

$\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ and preliminary simulation results clearly indicated that the former option is better than the latter. Therefore, only the choice $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ (or $\mathcal{HN}(\theta)$) for $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ is considered in this simulation study.

The corresponding classical kernel estimators are:

$$\hat{\Delta}_3(X_i) = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \frac{\min\{\hat{f}_1(X_{ij}), \hat{f}_2(X_{ij}), \hat{f}_3(X_{ij})\}}{\hat{f}_i(X_{ij})}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

and

$$\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \frac{1}{3} \left(\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1) + \hat{\Delta}_3(X_2) + \hat{\Delta}_3(X_3) \right)$$

where $\hat{f}_i(t)$ is the classical kernel estimator based on a sample i and at point t . The smoothing parameters for the multiplicative (b_i) and classical (h_i) kernel estimates are computed by using the formulas (see, Section 2.2):

$$b_i = 1.0834 S_i n^{-1/9} \quad \text{and} \quad h_i = 0.9 A_i n_i^{-1/5}.$$

The simulation results related to the above estimators are presented in Tables

4.2 - 4.5 .

Tables 4.6 - 4.9 give the results of the proposed multiplicative kernel estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_k$ for $k = 3$ that developed in Chapter 3 and the corresponding classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_k$, $k = 3$ (see Section, 3.3 and Section, 3.4).

4.4 Quantitative Measurements

The quantitative measures will be computed based on 1000 replications. For each considered estimator, the quantitative measures; Relative Bias (RB), Relative Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Efficiency (EFF) were computed. The following are the rules for these quantitative measures:

The relative bias (*RB*) is,

$$RB = \frac{\hat{E}(estimator) - exact}{exact}.$$

The relative root of mean squared error (*RMSE*) is,

$$RMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\widehat{MSE}(estimator)}}{exact},$$

where,

$$\hat{E}(\hat{\Delta}) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{1000} \hat{\Delta}_{(j)}}{1000} \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{MSE}(\hat{\Delta}) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{1000} (\hat{\Delta}_{(j)} - \Delta_{(j)})^2}{1000}.$$

The efficiency of the proposed estimator with respect to the corresponding classical kernel estimator is defined by,

$$EFF = \frac{\widehat{MSE}(classical\ kernel\ estimator)}{\widehat{MSE}(proposed\ estimator)}.$$

For instance, the values of the efficiencies in the tables of simulation results were calculated as follows:

If the multiplicative kernel estimate of Δ_3 is $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1)$ then the corresponding classical kernel estimate of Δ_3 is $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1)$ and the efficiency is,

$$EFF = \frac{\widehat{MSE}(\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1))}{\widehat{MSE}(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1))},$$

while the efficiency of $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is,

$$EFF = \frac{\widehat{MSE}(\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3))}{\widehat{MSE}(\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3))}.$$

4.5 Simulation Results

The results of the simulation study were obtained by generating data from 16 cases shown in Table 4.1, which also included the exact value Δ_3 corresponding to each case.

The simulation results in Tables 4.2 - 4.5 are related to the estimators of the classical kernel and the proposed multiplicative kernel, which were derived based on the idea of writing the overlapping coefficient as an expected value for some function and then performing the estimation process (see Section 2.4 and Section 2.5). Our comment on the results related to these estimators is included in the below subsection with title “Simulation Results (I)”.

While the results of Tables 4.6 - 4.9 are related to the proposed multiplicative kernel estimator and the corresponding classical kernel estimator that were developed based on the idea of approximating the integral of Δ_3 and then performing the estimation process. These estimators were derived in chapter three (see Section 3.3 and Section 3.4). The results related to these estimators are commented in the subsection below under the title “Simulation Results (II)”.

4.5.1 Simulation results (I)

Based on the simulation results of Tables 4.2 - 4.5, we generally conclude the following:

1. Regarding the relative bias (RB), in almost all cases under study, the RB values associated with the classical kernel estimator are negative, but this is not the case for the proposed multiplicative kernel estimator. For classical and multiplicative estimators, the absolute value of RB often decreases with increasing sample sizes, and its value often becomes negligible as sample sizes increase. Based on RB values alone, it is difficult to argue that one of the classical or multiplicative methods gives better estimators than the other.
2. Considering different estimators corresponding to $\Delta_3(X_i), i = 1, 2, 3$, the performance of these estimators, whether related to the classical kernel method (i.e. $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_i), i = 1, 2, 3$) or the multiplicative kernel method (i.e.

$\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_i)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$), is volatile, such that their performances are good in certain cases and bad in some other cases. For example, the performance of the two multiplicative estimators $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_2)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_3)$ for half-normal distribution (Cases 13, 14, 15 and 16) is better than that of the multiplicative estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1)$. However, the opposite is true in –for example- Cases 3, 4, 6, 7 and 12. The same can be said about the classical estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_i)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$. By comparing these estimators with those corresponding to $\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ (i.e. the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and the multiplicative kernel estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$), we notice that the performances of the latter have more stability and higher reliability. This is not strange or surprising since the estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ are the average of the estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_i)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_i)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$ respectively. So, we will increase the focus of our comparison on the two estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$.

3. For the various considered estimators, their relative root of mean squared error (RMSE) decreases for increasing sample sizes. This indicates that as the sample size increases, the accuracy of the estimators improves, as reflected in the reduced RMSE. That is, these results show that the estimators achieve the consistency property, which is considered one of the most important statistical characteristics of a good estimator.

4. By examining the values of RMSE associated with both the classical kernel and multiplicative kernel estimators, we find, in general, that their associated values are smaller when the true value of Δ_3 is large, while the RMSE associated with them increases when the true value of Δ_3 is small. For example, for a normal distribution (Case 5 with $(n_1, n_2, n_3) = (20, 20, 20)$), the exact value of $\Delta_3 = 0.8415$, the RMSE value of $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is 0.1813 (it is 0.2135 for $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$), but in Case 8 of the same distribution and the same sample sizes, in which the true value of Δ_3 is 0.0965, the value of the RMSE of $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ equals to 0.4892 (it is 0.4988 for $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$). That is, in general, the value of RMSE of both estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is inversely proportional to the true value of Δ_3 . That is, the classical and multiplicative kernel estimators estimate a large Δ_3 value better than they estimate a small Δ_3 value.

5. Now we would like to compare the RMSE values of the two estimators $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$. For more simplicity, this comparison can be achieved by examining the efficiency (EFF) values in the last column of each table. If the EFF value is greater than one, this indicates that the multiplicative kernel estimator, $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ outperforms the corresponding classical kernel estimator, $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$. Except for Cases 3

and 12, the efficiency value for the remaining cases was greater than one, which indicates that the multiplicative kernel estimator performs better than the classical kernel estimator. Even Case 3, the EFF value is close to one, which means that the achievement of the two estimators is rather similar. In fact, the performance of the proposed estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is better than that of estimator $\hat{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ for 14 out of 16 cases considered in this study.

6. Finally, the multiplicative kernel estimators generally exhibit better performance in terms of their RMSE (and hence in terms of efficiency), so we recommend using the estimators resulting from the multiplicative kernel method.

4.5.2 Simulation results (II)

Tables 4.6 - 4.9 provide simulation results related to the multiplicative kernel estimator and the corresponding classical kernel estimator of Δ_3 developed in Chapter (3). After studying and analyzing these results, we conclude the following:

1. In general, the absolute value of RB for both the multiplicative kernel estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3$ and the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_3$ of Δ_3 decrease with increasing sample sizes. It becomes negligible for large sample sizes.

2. For the classical ($\hat{\Delta}_3$) and multiplicative ($\tilde{\Delta}_3$) kernel estimators, regardless of the value of the parameter θ , the RMSE values decrease when the sample size increases, which means that both estimators are consistent.
3. The values of RMSE of both the classical and multiplicative kernel estimators increase when the exact value of Δ_3 is small, while it is lower when the exact value of Δ_3 is large.
4. For efficiency, in the majority cases, the efficiency value was greater than one, which indicates that the multiplicative kernel estimator performs better than the classical kernel estimator.
5. We also note that the performance of the three proposed estimators, $\tilde{\Delta}_3$ ($\theta = 1$), $\tilde{\Delta}_3$ ($\theta = 2$) and $\tilde{\Delta}_3(\theta = MLE)$ is similar in most cases except for some cases, in which the performance of $\tilde{\Delta}_3$ ($\theta = 2$) becomes much worse compared to the other two estimators. Therefore, we can conclude - in general - that the performance of the proposed estimator developed based on trapezoidal rule is sensitive in some cases to the selection of the transformation function. Based on our numerical findings, the choice of $\theta = 1$ or $\theta = MLE$ is highly acceptable. However, we recommend estimating θ according to the available data. That is, we recommend using the suggested estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(\theta = MLE)$.

Table (4.2). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates when the data are simulated from an **extreme** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3(X_1)$	$\Delta_3(X_2)$	$\Delta_3(X_3)$	$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$
		Case 1, $\Delta_3 = 0.8844$				
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.236	-0.215	-0.219	-0.223
		RMSE	0.2568	0.2355	0.2394	0.2426
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.181	-0.174	-0.156	-0.170
		RMSE	0.2069	0.2021	0.1842	0.1944
		EFF	1.540	1.358	1.690	1.559
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0985	-0.0799	-0.0830	-0.0871
		RMSE	0.1131	0.0947	0.09712	0.1013
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0662	-0.0524	-0.0313	-0.0500
		RMSE	0.0896	0.0764	0.0580	0.0723
		EFF	1.593	1.534	2.80	1.962
		Case 2, $\Delta_3 = 0.6397$				
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.155	-0.0944	-0.126	-0.125
		RMSE	0.2222	0.1855	0.2010	0.1996
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.127	-0.0457	-0.0825	-0.0851
		RMSE	0.2072	0.1819	0.1879	0.1823
		EFF	1.150	1.041	1.145	1.198
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0547	-0.00644	-0.0247	-0.0286
		RMSE	0.1112	0.09427	0.09525	0.09805
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0543	0.0553	0.0243	0.0084
		RMSE	0.1116	0.1148	0.0998	0.0950
		EFF	0.993	0.674	0.910	1.065
		Case 3, $\Delta_3 = 0.3108$				
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0763	-0.0371	-0.0667	-0.0600
		RMSE	0.3008	0.3201	0.2831	0.2971
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.177	0.0526	-0.0408	-0.0550
		RMSE	0.3151	0.3680	0.3182	0.3013
		EFF	0.912	0.756	0.792	0.972
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0148	0.0196	0.00811	0.00431
		RMSE	0.1758	0.1797	0.1671	0.1731
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0986	0.169	0.0734	0.0481
		RMSE	0.1881	0.2662	0.1858	0.1747
		EFF	0.874	0.456	0.809	0.981
		Case 4, $\Delta_3 = 0.0878$				
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.169	-0.0534	-0.140	-0.120
		RMSE	0.4277	0.6195	0.5558	0.5018
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0510	-0.202	0.0653	-0.0285
		RMSE	0.5058	0.5702	0.6667	0.4783
		EFF	0.715	1.180	0.695	1.101
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0914	0.00777	-0.0437	-0.0424
		RMSE	0.2254	0.2749	0.2562	0.2416
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0850	-0.110	0.261	0.0787
		RMSE	0.2456	0.2783	0.3879	0.2112
		EFF	0.842	0.976	0.436	1.309

Table (4.3). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates when the data are simulated from **normal** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3(X_1)$	$\Delta_3(X_2)$	$\Delta_3(X_3)$	$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$
Case 5, $\Delta_3 = 0.8415$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.182	-0.184	-0.185	-0.184
		RMSE	0.2139	0.2156	0.2158	0.2135
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.146	-0.145	-0.145	-0.146
		RMSE	0.1852	0.1849	0.1839	0.1813
		EFF	1.335	1.361	1.377	1.387
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0598	-0.0576	-0.0562	-0.0578
		RMSE	0.08718	0.08373	0.08270	0.0841
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0357	-0.0413	-0.0406	-0.0392
		RMSE	0.0741	0.0774	0.0771	0.0752
		EFF	1.384	1.171	1.150	1.249
Case 6, $\Delta_3 = 0.6171$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0732	-0.0699	-0.0720	-0.0717
		RMSE	0.1870	0.1827	0.1892	0.1840
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0841	-0.0912	-0.0860	-0.0871
		RMSE	0.2025	0.2101	0.2010	0.1964
		EFF	0.853	0.756	0.886	0.877
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0069	0.0129	0.00903	0.00963
		RMSE	0.1030	0.09831	0.1009	0.1003
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0142	-0.0221	-0.0189	-0.0184
		RMSE	0.1014	0.1045	0.1034	0.1001
		EFF	1.031	0.885	0.953	1.003
Case 7, $\Delta_3 = 0.4235$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0577	-0.0785	-0.0041	-0.0468
		RMSE	0.2341	0.2318	0.2465	0.2322
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0716	-0.0549	-0.116	-0.0808
		RMSE	0.2104	0.2173	0.2830	0.2236
		EFF	1.239	1.137	0.759	1.078
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0048	0.0007	0.0402	0.0152
		RMSE	0.1283	0.1201	0.1333	0.1256
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0217	-0.0209	-0.0286	-0.0238
		RMSE	0.1170	0.1180	0.1355	0.1176
		EFF	1.203	1.036	0.968	1.140
Case 8, $\Delta_3 = 0.0965$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.169	0.0537	-0.0472	-0.0543
		RMSE	0.4383	0.5193	0.6594	0.4988
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0421	-0.171	-0.134	-0.0876
		RMSE	0.5391	0.5339	0.6343	0.4892
		EFF	0.661	0.946	1.081	1.040
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0868	0.0862	0.0228	0.0074
		RMSE	0.2294	0.2490	0.2659	0.2298
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.125	-0.0824	-0.0735	-0.0102
		RMSE	0.2617	0.2317	0.2559	0.1965
		EFF	0.768	1.155	1.079	1.367

Table (4.4). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates when the data are simulated from **Weibull** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3(X_1)$	$\Delta_3(X_2)$	$\Delta_3(X_3)$	$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$
Case 9, $\Delta_3 = 0.8975$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.224	-0.213	-0.209	-0.215
		RMSE	0.2443	0.2335	0.2290	0.2343
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.133	-0.131	-0.130	-0.131
		RMSE	0.1593	0.1575	0.1566	0.1554
		EFF	2.352	2.196	2.138	2.273
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0892	-0.0805	-0.0778	-0.0825
		RMSE	0.1053	0.0956	0.0931	0.0977
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0385	-0.0377	-0.0280	-0.0347
		RMSE	0.0663	0.0639	0.0583	0.0615
		EFF	2.52	2.242	2.55	2.52
Case 10, $\Delta_3 = 0.6644$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0854	-0.109	-0.0865	-0.0936
		RMSE	0.1847	0.1906	0.1831	0.1835
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0506	-0.0138	-0.0127	0.00805
		RMSE	0.1579	0.1472	0.1631	0.1484
		EFF	1.368	1.678	1.260	1.528
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0085	-0.0211	-0.0087	-0.0128
		RMSE	0.0983	0.0947	0.0951	0.0954
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0925	0.0299	0.0357	0.0527
		RMSE	0.1268	0.0876	0.0976	0.1004
		EFF	0.601	1.169	0.948	0.903
Case 11, $\Delta_3 = 0.4429$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.146	-0.0749	-0.140	-0.120
		RMSE	0.2545	0.2530	0.2557	0.2487
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0002	0.0079	-0.0116	-0.0013
		RMSE	0.1899	0.2506	0.1997	0.2053
		EFF	1.796	1.020	1.639	1.468
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0650	-0.0144	-0.0504	-0.0433
		RMSE	0.1299	0.1219	0.1223	0.1222
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0436	0.0443	0.0242	0.0374
		RMSE	0.1136	0.1338	0.1046	0.1151
		EFF	1.307	0.831	1.367	1.128
Case 12, $\Delta_3 = 0.1089$						
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.182	-0.0648	-0.204	-0.150
		RMSE	0.3891	0.5636	0.4010	0.4180
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0876	0.196	0.122	0.135
		RMSE	0.3606	0.6463	0.3820	0.4188
		EFF	1.165	0.760	1.102	0.996
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0669	0.0272	-0.0393	-0.0263
		RMSE	0.2035	0.2757	0.2015	0.2151
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.142	0.260	0.185	0.196
		RMSE	0.2301	0.3879	0.2593	0.2786
		EFF	0.782	0.505	0.604	0.596

Table (4.5). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates when the data are simulated from **half-normal** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3(X_1)$	$\Delta_3(X_2)$	$\Delta_3(X_3)$	$\Delta_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$
			Case 13, $\Delta_3 = 0.8925$			
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.182	-0.184	-0.185	-0.184
		RMSE	0.2139	0.2156	0.2158	0.2135
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.116	-0.121	-0.122	-0.119
		RMSE	0.1486	0.1531	0.1528	0.1504
		EFF	2.072	2.141	2.227	2.160
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0598	-0.0576	-0.0562	-0.0578
		RMSE	0.0872	0.0837	0.0827	0.0841
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0337	-0.0374	-0.0336	-0.0349
		RMSE	0.0662	0.0667	0.0645	0.0655
		EFF	2.029	2.148	2.293	2.162
			Case 14, $\Delta_3 = 0.6127$			
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0732	-0.0699	-0.0720	-0.0717
		RMSE	0.1870	0.1827	0.1892	0.1840
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0588	-0.0670	-0.0769	-0.0676
		RMSE	0.1797	0.1717	0.1675	0.1679
		EFF	1.161	1.315	1.680	1.409
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0069	0.0129	0.0090	0.00963
		RMSE	0.1030	0.0983	0.1009	0.1003
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0102	-0.0155	-0.0213	-0.0157
		RMSE	0.0958	0.0819	0.0817	0.0846
		EFF	0.959	1.297	1.504	1.253
			Case 15, $\Delta_3 = 0.3529$			
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0577	-0.0785	-0.0041	-0.0468
		RMSE	0.2341	0.2318	0.2465	0.2322
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0288	-0.0704	-0.0712	-0.0568
		RMSE	0.2802	0.2030	0.2026	0.2156
		EFF	0.993	1.477	1.680	1.373
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0048	0.0007	0.0402	0.0152
		RMSE	0.1283	0.1201	0.1333	0.1256
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0103	-0.0125	-0.0162	-0.0062
		RMSE	0.1746	0.1123	0.1113	0.1268
		EFF	1.00	1.607	1.687	1.407
			Case 16, $\Delta_3 = 0.1583$			
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.169	0.0537	-0.0472	-0.0543
		RMSE	0.4383	0.5193	0.6594	0.4988
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0643	-0.116	-0.0614	-0.0805
		RMSE	0.4932	0.2645	0.3583	0.3087
		EFF	0.942	1.781	1.031	1.332
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0868	0.0862	0.0228	0.0074
		RMSE	0.2294	0.2490	0.2659	0.2298
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0145	-0.0465	-0.0146	-0.0252
		RMSE	0.3146	0.1403	0.1629	0.1771
		EFF	0.976	1.926	1.326	1.476

Table (4.6). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates (approximation method) when the data are simulated from an **extreme** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3 (\theta = 1)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = 2)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = MLE)$
			Case 1, $\Delta_3 = 0.8844$		
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.221	-0.353	-0.213
		RMSE	0.2388	0.3616	0.2313
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.191	-0.347	-0.184
		RMSE	0.2115	0.3546	0.2074
		EFF	1.275	1.040	1.244
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0874	-0.189	-0.0832
		RMSE	0.1011	0.1951	0.09757
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0629	-0.191	-0.0573
		RMSE	0.0828	0.1952	0.0799
		EFF	1.492	0.999	1.490
Case 2, $\Delta_3 = 0.6397$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.136	-0.356	-0.106
		RMSE	0.1993	0.3766	0.1846
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.123	-0.386	-0.0938
		RMSE	0.1937	0.4030	0.1906
		EFF	1.058	0.873	0.938
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0324	-0.197	-0.0185
		RMSE	0.09676	0.2093	0.09478
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0084	-0.218	0.0097
		RMSE	0.0934	0.2250	0.1023
		EFF	1.074	0.865	0.858
Case 3, $\Delta_3 = 0.3108$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0197	-0.139	-0.0178
		RMSE	0.2804	0.2797	0.2843
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0589	-0.187	-0.0567
		RMSE	0.3202	0.3041	0.3217
		EFF	0.767	0.846	0.781
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0259	-0.0504	0.0253
		RMSE	0.1722	0.1626	0.1732
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0788	-0.0336	0.0793
		RMSE	0.2083	0.1443	0.2092
		EFF	0.683	1.270	0.685
Case 4, $\Delta_3 = 0.0878$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0517	0.0647	0.0526
		RMSE	0.4650	0.4885	0.4702
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0873	-0.0828	-0.0895
		RMSE	0.4488	0.4665	0.4476
		EFF	1.073	1.096	1.103
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0708	0.0688	0.0708
		RMSE	0.2406	0.2415	0.2406
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0928	0.0930	0.0927
		RMSE	0.2345	0.2363	0.2340
		EFF	1.053	1.045	1.058

Table (4.7). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates (approximation method) when the data are simulated from **normal** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3 (\theta = 1)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = 2)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = MLE)$
			Case 5, $\Delta_3 = 0.8415$		
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.174	-0.213	-0.174
		RMSE	0.2022	0.2345	0.2019
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.160	-0.180	-0.160
		RMSE	0.1933	0.2060	0.1933
		EFF	1.094	1.295	1.091
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0561	-0.0675	-0.0561
		RMSE	0.0823	0.0898	0.08229
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0426	-0.0483	-0.0426
		RMSE	0.0771	0.0787	0.0771
		EFF	1.140	1.302	1.140
Case 6, $\Delta_3 = 0.6171$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0589	-0.0846	-0.0583
		RMSE	0.1726	0.1794	0.1726
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.106	-0.117	-0.106
		RMSE	0.2079	0.2091	0.2080
		EFF	0.689	0.736	0.688
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.00965	0.00270	0.00970
		RMSE	0.09793	0.09701	0.09789
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0224	-0.0255	-0.0224
		RMSE	0.1022	0.1013	0.1022
		EFF	0.919	0.917	0.918
Case 7, $\Delta_3 = 0.4235$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0188	-0.165	-0.0195
		RMSE	0.2156	0.2473	0.2150
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.104	-0.194	-0.104
		RMSE	0.2322	0.2573	0.2320
		EFF	0.862	0.923	0.859
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0269	-0.0194	0.0269
		RMSE	0.1239	0.1090	0.1239
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0274	-0.0549	-0.0274
		RMSE	0.1231	0.1163	0.1231
		EFF	1.013	0.878	1.013
Case 8, $\Delta_3 = 0.0965$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0754	0.0756	0.0772
		RMSE	0.4725	0.4715	0.4733
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.197	-0.202	-0.204
		RMSE	0.4531	0.4513	0.4523
		EFF	1.087	1.091	1.095
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0894	0.0898	0.0900
		RMSE	0.2397	0.2393	0.2394
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0826	-0.0823	-0.0825
		RMSE	0.1953	0.1951	0.1952
		EFF	1.507	1.505	1.504

Table (4.8). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates (approximation method) when the data are simulated from **Weibull** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3 (\theta = 1)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = 2)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = MLE)$
			Case 9, $\Delta_3 = 0.8975$		
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.227	-0.210	-0.210
		RMSE	0.2432	0.2274	0.2271
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.170	-0.151	-0.150
		RMSE	0.1849	0.1696	0.1693
		EFF	1.730	1.798	1.800
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0821	-0.0815	-0.0814
		RMSE	0.0973	0.09638	0.09632
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0533	-0.0516	-0.0515
		RMSE	0.0723	0.0717	0.0716
		EFF	1.810	1.808	1.809
Case 10, $\Delta_3 = 0.6644$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.231	-0.0821	-0.0815
		RMSE	0.2642	0.1719	0.1712
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.165	-0.0089	-0.0097
		RMSE	0.2001	0.1382	0.1382
		EFF	1.744	1.547	1.535
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0408	-0.0098	-0.0099
		RMSE	0.1001	0.0925	0.09253
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0028	0.0379	0.0374
		RMSE	0.0747	0.0884	0.0882
		EFF	1.795	1.095	1.101
Case 11, $\Delta_3 = 0.4429$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0959	-0.106	-0.101
		RMSE	0.2285	0.2295	0.2287
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0023	-0.0139	-0.0082
		RMSE	0.1813	0.1799	0.1812
		EFF	1.589	1.627	1.592
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0290	-0.0324	-0.0307
		RMSE	0.1145	0.1149	0.1147
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.0401	0.0355	0.0376
		RMSE	0.1079	0.1059	0.1069
		EFF	1.127	1.176	1.151
Case 12, $\Delta_3 = 0.1089$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.133	-0.0266	-0.0249
		RMSE	0.3710	0.3692	0.3709
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.258	0.381	0.379
		RMSE	0.4511	0.5322	0.5337
		EFF	0.676	0.481	0.483
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0537	0.0507	0.0499
		RMSE	0.2058	0.2031	0.2040
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	0.376	0.395	0.396
		RMSE	0.4191	0.4362	0.4373
		EFF	0.2411	0.2169	0.2176

Table (4.9). Relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the classical and multiplicative kernel estimates (approximation method) when the data are simulated from **half-normal** distribution.

(n_1, n_2, n_3)			$\Delta_3 (\theta = 1)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = 2)$	$\Delta_3 (\theta = MLE)$
			Case 13, $\Delta_3 = 0.8925$		
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.174	-0.213	-0.174
		RMSE	0.2022	0.2345	0.2019
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.144	-0.160	-0.142
		RMSE	0.1672	0.1801	0.1658
		EFF	1.671	1.598	1.679
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0561	-0.0675	-0.0561
		RMSE	0.0823	0.0898	0.0823
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0566	-0.0633	-0.0556
		RMSE	0.0774	0.0820	0.0767
		EFF	1.556	1.535	1.559
Case 14, $\Delta_3 = 0.6127$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0589	-0.0846	-0.0583
		RMSE	0.1726	0.1794	0.1726
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.116	-0.151	-0.0983
		RMSE	0.1808	0.2027	0.1722
		EFF	1.275	1.226	1.296
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0097	0.0027	0.0097
		RMSE	0.0979	0.0970	0.0979
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0491	-0.0639	-0.0409
		RMSE	0.0897	0.0975	0.0863
		EFF	1.215	1.184	1.230
Case 15, $\Delta_3 = 0.3529$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0188	-0.165	-0.0195
		RMSE	0.2156	0.2473	0.2150
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.111	-0.154	-0.0881
		RMSE	0.2090	0.2304	0.2024
		EFF	1.322	1.249	1.355
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0269	-0.0194	0.0269
		RMSE	0.1239	0.1090	0.1239
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0416	-0.0591	-0.0304
		RMSE	0.1138	0.1194	0.1118
		EFF	1.515	1.421	1.570
Case 16, $\Delta_3 = 0.1583$					
(20,20,20)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0754	0.0756	0.0772
		RMSE	0.4725	0.4715	0.4733
	multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.122	-0.151	-0.146
		RMSE	0.2539	0.2659	0.2657
		EFF	1.461	1.421	1.421
(50,100,150)	Classical Kernel Estimate	RB	0.0894	0.0898	0.0900
		RMSE	0.2397	0.2393	0.2394
	Multiplicative kernel Estimate	RB	-0.0530	-0.0647	-0.0605
		RMSE	0.1392	0.1428	0.1419
		EFF	1.699	1.643	1.660

CHAPTER FIVE

Conclusions And Future Works

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we present the overall findings and a few recommendations that can be used in research projects in the future.

5.2 General Conclusions

After study the simulation results, we can summarize the most important of these results as follow:

1. The simulation results clearly showed the superiority of the estimators proposed using the multiplicative kernel over those generated using the classical kernel for the majority of the cases studied.
2. The performance of the estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ was compared with the performance of the estimator $\tilde{\Delta}_3(\theta = MLE)$ we can conclude that there was a convergence between the results, however $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ was performs better than $\tilde{\Delta}_3(\theta = MLE)$ in many of the cases considered, this is contrary to the results of the classical kernel estimator.

3. The general main result based on our numerical results we recommend using $\tilde{\Delta}_3(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ then $\tilde{\Delta}_3(\theta = MLE)$ to estimate the Weitzman overlapping coefficient Δ_3 .

5.3 Suggestions For Future Works

There are a lot of recommendations that may be made that are connected to this thesis. The most important of them are:

- We can attempt to generalize the other overlapping coefficients, such as the Matusita and Marusita coefficients, and then to estimate them using the same methods of this thesis.
- The possibility of applying the same techniques used in this thesis but by using the non-parametric method to estimate $\hat{f}_i^*(x)$ such as the fourth-order kernel method (Silverman, 1986), the variable kernel method (Breiman et al., 1977), or the local bandwidth kernel method (Schucany, 1989).
- We can use the multiplicative kernel estimator $\tilde{f}_i(x), i = 1, 2$, to make inference about the well-known problem, stress-strength reliability ($X > Y$), (Altarabsheh, 2023), where X and Y are independent random variable.

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